

Israel's Hollywood: Nationalism, war and trauma through *Waltz with Bashir*

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1.Introduction

Teens nowadays have turned away from books or magazines spending more time in touch with online media, TV and cinema as nowadays books have stopped being read for pleasure and other digital arts have taken over (Sliwa,2018,para.1).

It is that, by using cinema as our tool we will look at Israel's national identity and war trauma as they are two big important aspects that still today are important to Israeli citizens as, the main point of the paper is to show that nationalism and identity are two imaginary constructs created for and by the human being to give itself a purpose.

This purpose needs to be shown or transferred to the people in a way so cinema as an audiovisual medium has the power to transmit it as a way of propaganda for the people to feel identified with it. Our research will start by exploring how cinema portrays reality and what mechanisms it uses for us to believe what we are seeing in reality..

We will use this knowledge to explain how these techniques serve as a way to make the spectator feel and attribute to themselves certain values and emotions that don't solely belong to them as, in the next step of my research, we will explore how nations and “imagine communities” form and how Israel's nationalism was shaped as we will also look into the ideological bases and principles of Zionism, which is “the recovery of the institutional nationhood, the restoration of the ancestral homeland”(Taylor,1972, pg.35).

For the treatment of this broad topic we will focus on the 1982 war and its aftermath, we will answer what trauma and future problems left and we will take a look at a piece of film to analyze not only war trauma but also how it affects Israel's population. *Waltz with Bashir* (2008) is an animated Israel film created by Israeli filmmaker Ari Folman. The film explores Folman's past and trauma as he tries to reconnect with the people he fought in the military. This movie treats topics of memory ,trauma, war and national identity, questioning imaginary concepts and what have done to them. We will dive deep using mechanisms of

psychoanalytic film analysis to see how this film creates a sense of identification for many Israeli people and how cinema is a way to project this traumas being also an open space for the assimilation and negotiation of political topics such as nationalism, war, trauma, memory, identity, social reality and many more.

2.Cinema: the portrayal of reality

Cinema as a cultural product and institution has been studied by academic researchers in the arts and humanities fields (Tan,2018, pg.1). When starting their research, Cinema in its first stages was not looking to tell a story but rather to show something as in its early stages it received the name of “cinema of attractions”. As Tom Gunning argues in Robert Knopf’s book *“The Cinema of Attractions”* “(...) it's the ability to show something”(Gunning,2005, pg.39), this approach will contrast with the future development of cinema as, cinema nowadays has taken a path more oriented towards telling stories rather than just showing itself. This approach of Cinema of Attractions collides with what author Christian Metz will analyze in the future as, Metz’s point of view relied more on a voyeuristic approach as he analyzes cinema from a narrative aspect (Gunning, 2005,pg.39). As a more exhibitionist movement, cinema of attractions differentiates from nowadays cinema as in cinema usually it is the camera that acts as our eye to not only serve our voyeuristic point of view but also to make it more realistic, in this early stages of cinema the actors recurrently look at the camera therefore breaking the suspension of disbelief that is fundamental in nowadays cinema.(Gunning, 2005, pg.39)

What Cinema of Attractions looks like is to catch the spectators eye in order to show itself as it is not the narrative aspect that is important, but rather is the spectacle and the way it's made that is important as cinema was relatively new at the time. In the early stages of cinema most films would rather just show simplistic events rather than a narrative plot as pictures of moving vehicles like trains were shown on this early films(Gunning,2005, p.40).The

voyeuristic aspect did not rely on the narrative but rather on how the machine worked as the early audience showed great interest in knowing how the Kinetoscope or the Vitascope worked (Gunning, 2005, pg. 40).

After years of development, cinema went on to instead of just showing itself, it showed reality and started to imitate it. One of the most important cinematic movements that transformed cinema in the medium we know today is the movement of the Russian formalism. It is in the early 1920's that one of the main figures behind this movement, Russian film director, Lev Kuleshov developed what is the "Kuleshov effect", it is in their article "*The Kuleshov Effect: Recreating the Classic Experiment*" where authors Stephen Prince and Wayne E. Hensley recalled what the Kuleshov experiment was and what it meant for cinema's further development. The effect was generated and created after Kuleshov did certain different film experiments during the 1920's as "(...) deriving from the series of editing experiments conducted by Lev Kuleshov in the late teens and early 1920s. | One experiment in particular-with the actor Mozhukin, child, soup, and coffin" (Hensley & Prince, 1992, pg. 59). What the experiment consisted of was in contraposing the different shots of Mozhukin, the child, the soup and the coffin and to see if they generated any type of effect between them. The Russian formalism movement was a movement that moved into analyzing film, structure and meaning as editing was a technique that allowed us to construct and deconstruct images and remake them into something different (Hensley & Prince, 1992, pg. 60). Hensley and Prince (1992) pointed out about Kuleschov's research that:

"Accordingly, his experiments seemed to demonstrate how cinematic meaning might be a creation wholly of the medium's manipulation, without any analogue with or correspondence to real physical reality" (pg. 60)

It is with this information that we can construct a definition to understand this effect as Kuleshov is an effect that is crucial in understanding how cinema constructs a "false" reality.

We can argue that the Kuleshov effect is the juxtaposition or contraposition of shots generate different meanings.

Kuleshov understood shots, not as images, but as signs that possessed semantic meaning as this semantic meant shots were able to create a narrative of their own as he said “The analogy with language was crucial for Kuleshov's project because it justified cinema as an orderly semiotic system possessing a kind of grammar that might be systematically investigated” (Hensley & Prince,1992,pg.62). Therefore we can add this to our definition and argue that the Kuleshov effect is the contraposition of shots that contain semantic and meaningful content, allowing for the creation of different meaning and sensations and that allow the spectator to feel emotions and immerse itself in the narrative aspect of the film they are watching.

The spectator watches a piece of film and it is through this contraposition that it identifies with the events that are undergoing. In order for us to watch a movie, we need to possess a sense of identification with what we are seeing on the screen.

In their text, “*Introduction to Cinematic Identifications*” authors Elizabeth Reich and Scott C. Richmond, discuss the previously mentioned scholar Christopher Metz approach on narrative films and cinematic identifications. Metz presents the concept of cinematic identifications as a way to understand how we interact and sufficiently believe what we are seeing on the screen. Metz establishes a distinction between two complementary processes which receive the names of primary identifications and secondary identifications. (Reich & Richmond,2015, pg.5)

It is important to clarify that this concept of cinematic identifications has still need to be taken more seriously as some scholars have failed to recognize the importance of this theory that as diverse as it ism it allows us to understand the complexity and diversity of the phenomenon of spectatorship (Reich & Richmond,2015, pg.6).

First of all we will explain the concept of secondary identifications “(...) because primary cinematic identification has remained too obscure, while secondary cinematic identification has seemed rather too obvious.”(Reich & Richmond,2015,pg.6). According to Metz on secondary identifications:

“For Metz, secondary cinematic identification is a catchall phrase that includes any identifications in which the spectator participates beyond the technical operation of the cinema—and not only with characters.”(Reich & Richmond,2015 pg.6)

So therefore we can argue that secondary identifications engage in a more emotional and political way that primary identifications do not. Primary identifications are more tied to technical and primal stages and set the principles and bases in order for secondary identifications to participate. As Metz argues, cinematic identifications happen like the so-called “mirror stage” would, Reich and Richmond (2015), point out scholar Laura Mulvey’s (1986) definition of mirror phase as she says:

“The mirror phase occurs at a time when the child's physical ambitions outstrip his motor capacity, with the result that his recognition of himself is joyous in that he imagines his mirror image to be more complete, more perfect than he experiences his own body.”(Mulvey,1986, as cited in Reich & Richmond,2016,pg.8)

It is with this information that we are able to construct a more simple and less complex definition of what Secondary Identifications are. Secondary Identifications act based on the Primary Identifications as, equal to the identification that undergoes in the mirror phase, we identify with the situation of what we are seeing as the screen is the one that mirrors reality.

While secondary identifications seem more obvious, on the other hand, primary identifications showcase a more obscure and complex approach. In cinema, “the spectator identifies with the camera, as a technological perceiver of the world.”(Reich & Richmond,2015,pg.12) and this aspect of it is crucial in order for us to understand primary identifications as it is the first in

the whole process of cinematic identifications. Primary identifications engage more with the technical and primal aspects cinema as, we ourselves identify with the camera as our point of view and then, after this relationship is settled, the political and emotional relationship takes place as we identify with an implied narrator that acts as imaginational locus of enunciation in the film text (Reich & Richmond,2015, pg.12).

In conclusion, having said this we can understand that this two levels of identification act on different stages as the primary level acts on the more technical and point of view aspect while the relationships, identifications, emotions and political aspects are part of the secondary level that the primary identifications help to create and it is there where our minds believe what we are seeing sometimes interpreting as reality. Both cinematic identifications and the Kuleshov effect are to psychoanalyze processes and theories that will help us to understand how cinema projects ideas and can influence someone into believing something that might not be entirely true. It is for my research, that I have decided to explore how does Israel's film industry use audiovisual arts in order to indoctrinate certain beliefs into its population as it offers a different point of view for topics like national identity, nationalism, war and trauma and can teach history and different aspects of its culture.

3.Anderson and Nationalism

Nationalism has become one of the most important aspects of human life and society as it has shaped a big part of contemporary history. For our research on how nationalism is represented in cinema we are going to explore the work of american sociologist Benedict Anderson as his book titled "*Imagined communities: reflections on the origin and spread of nationalism*" (1983) will be crucial to understand how nationalism works and how it can be implemented into people's head through the audiovisual arts.

In his book, Anderson sets a theory on how national identity and the phenomenon of nationalism is generated as, in his text *Anderson and the Imagined Nation* (2016), researcher

Marc Sanjaume i Calvet, explains how does Anderson think that nationalism was created as he says “In his view, nationalism was born out of Capitalism, the Press, the novel and vernacular languages.”(Sanjaume i Calvet,2016, pg.65). It is this concept that quickly spread through Europe as this new concept, according to Anderson, was created because of the breakage with divine right and a new way of thinking was needed. It was specially the press and literature that influenced the creation of the nation state as this new notion of nationalism was shared between equals and common equals (Sanjaume i Calvet,2016,pg.65).

In Anderson's vision, nations are a product of modernity and are what he calls “imagined communities”. He believes that nations are shaped by the press and the bounds that the community says, therefore, not being able to predate nationalism (Sanjaume i Calvet,2016, pg.65, pg.66).

It was the spread of nationalism that was consolidated during the 1980’s as a product of the modern era. This construct of nationalism and, because it is an “imagined community”, argues that it enters in the same category as belonging to a religion or kinship in general.(Sanjaume i Calvet,2016 pg.66). As Sanjaume i Calvet (2016) argues about Anderson’s theories, nationalism was not generated naturally as:

“(…)the national narrative did not appear out of nothing but rather from a pre-existing cultural and institution fabric that make they viable, providing the raw materials for an ‘archaeology’ that allowed the growth of a sense of belonging.”(pg.68)

Therefore, we can conclude that social beliefs of nationalism, religion or identity and cultural customs are born out of a cultural fabric in order for us to have something or somewhere to belong.

4.Israel’s film industry

In his work “*Israeli Cinema: East/West and the Politics of Representation* by Ella Shohat; *Israeli Cinema: Identities in Motion* by Miri Talmon and Yaron Peleg”(2011), Nana Asfour

recalls Ella Shohat's quote on Israel cinema as she said "Israeli society and Israeli cinema are above all characterized by contradiction and ambivalence," (Asfour,2011, pg.70), this quote can summarize what Israel's film industry is all about as it has been influenced by many topics that have contradicted themselves throughout its existence.

Israeli cinema began before the creation of the state of Israel in 1948 as first we are going to explain the pre-state Israel films and then we are going to explore the film industry since 1948. The Israeli film industry started with Yaacov Ben Dov, who was the first person to own a movie camera in Palestine and recorded numerous documentaries such as the arrival of General Edmund Allenby in Ottoman Palestine in 1917 (Harris,2015, pg.221). It was decades after this event that the first full-Jewish feature film had been produced in the year 1932, when Palestine became part of the British mandate, the film, is called *Oded ha Noded* and was created by Nathan Axelrod, a Russian filmmaker who came from Russia and was believed to be trained in the Russian film industry by Sergei Eisenstein, one of Russia's most prolific filmmakers (Erens,1981, pg.60).

When talking about the first Israeli films, Nana Asfour shares in his text what Shohat thought about this early Israeli films as she said "As she notes, these films exalted the status of the newly arrived Jewish pioneers, who represented knowledge and progress, and were hailed as modernizers by "making the desert bloom"" (Asfour,2011, pg.71), also other topics included the transformation of, as Asfour points out "(...)of the weakling Diasporic Old Jew into a brawny New Jew."(Asfour,2011, pg.71), and Zionist theories as, in early Israel cinema it was the effects of of Zionist beliefs that left a mark on this audiovisual art as Asfour calls this effects to be "unassailable"(Asfour,2011 pg.71).

It was following the war that what was most released during these times were documentaries and feature films became restricted as it was mostly done by American or British filmmakers (Erens,1981, pg.60). It was during this times that "—Israeli filmmakers often looked abroad

or to new immigrants from Germany, England, and America, who had gained experience in their native homes”(Harris,2015, pg.222), this meant that during the postwar period it was british filmmakers who had the most influence over future productions.

We can see that before the creation of its country, Israel had a film industry based on documentaries and some feature films that talked about social issues, war and zionism. In the year 1948, the state of Israel was created and its film industry started to evolve and it was during this period that one the most famous films in Israel was released, “*Hill 24 doesn't answer*”(1955), which was shot with almost an entire israeli cast and talked about the jewish effort to defend Hill 24 during the 1948 Independence war. This film talked about masculinity, heroism and war and also “The transformation from diasporic Jew to New Jew and its concomitant dismissal of the Holocaust survivor, who failed to metamorphose, symbolized the centrality of Hebrewism in Israeli film”(Harris,2015, pg.223). This film, which became a box office hit during the 1950's came to symbolize the Zionist heroism of the soldiers of that era (Asfour,2011, pg.71).

Later on during the 1960's this “Heroic films” continued to well as most of them had been showing the polarity between the good Israeli protagonist and the evil arab villain. It was also that, during the 1960's a new counter culture appeared which were the *bourekas* which Naaman defines as “The "B" movies of the 1970s-mostly comedies, with some melo-dramas-are known as bourekas, after a popular Middle Eastern filo pastry”(Naaman,2001,pg.37)

As more wars and international conflicts appeared it was during the 1980's that “(...)marked the advent of a newly energized political cinema that criticized the Israeli occupation in the West Bank, Gaza Strip and South Lebanon”(Asfour,2011,pg.71) and, later on during the 1990's, the nationalist ethos of those years had vanished.

Later on, during the 2000's a new trend of Israeli films appeared as the Israeli-Palestinian conflict was starting to be treated in a different ways as "(...) many Israelis find themselves torn between the unwilling- ness to be victims yet again and the difficulty of accepting the role of the aggressor."(Asfour,2011, pg.71). It is films like *Waltz with Bashr* (2008) that follow this new wave as they differ from the previous biased nationalist narratives of Israel and treat the topic from a different perspective showing a more realistic side to the plot as, wars like the first lebanon war have left a mark on, not only the soldiers but also its population. In the next part of the paper we will discuss the topics of war and trauma.

5. Lebanon: War and Trauma

When studying and researching about the conflict between Israel and Palestine, it is also that we need to include the conflicts that Israel has with nations like Syria or Lebanon. In the different wars that Israel has participated in there are three main factors that have conditioned this wars which, according to Sayigh (1983) can be:

"Three basic factors have always affected the Israeli-Palestinian military confrontation: the physical dispersal of the Palestinian population, Israel's huge military and technological lead, and the political and topographical nature of the surrounding Arab states"(pg.24)

It is with the first factor that we have seen wars taking place in different parts of the Arab countries against Israel because of the presence of Palestinians in those places. This territory expansion of the PLO (Palestine Liberation Organization) happens because of the freedom that Arab countries give them to accomplish their purpose as, Sayigh argues "The policies of the Arab states surrounding Israel have an obvious influence on the freedom of the PLO to carry out armed action against Israel(...)"(Sayigh,1983, pg.25). There is one specific area that has favored the PLO for many strategic reasons, being South Lebanon because of its hills, vegetation and population. Yet South Lebanon offers Israel the advantages of better

reconnaissance, more effective air action and other more tactical advantages. Israel had certain disadvantages because, since it was limited to specific approach axes for major ground force movements across its borders as this encourages reliance on air portability, Israel has managed without the shift from ground to airborne forces (Sayigh,1983, pg.26).

It was the PLO's presence in Lebanon that caused what would be called the "First Lebanon War" that lasted 3 years, from 1982 to 1985. We will take a short look into the Lebanon war of 1982 as, in *Waltz with Bashir* (2008), it is the war that all the characters are involved in.

For the IDF (Israel Defence Forces) the main objective, according to Sayigh was "The political and strategic aim of the 1982 invasion was, therefore, the destruction of the PLO and its elimination as a principal actor in the Middle East conflict."(Sayigh,1983, pg.32). For this, the IDF drafted over 120.000 men and the clear target, according to Sayigh (1983) was known, as:

"It is evident that Beirut was a target of the IDF from the outset. There may well have been any number of contingency plans to deal with unexpected developments or delays at the strategic or tactical levels-the advance into the Beqaa Valley and the axis of approach to Beirut were two instances-but they probably all retained Beirut as the basic objective"(pg.33).

It was then that, in June 1982, the IDF launched a strike on Beirut for the first time. It was from 1975 until 1990 that Lebanon had been going through a civil war that saw different militias like the LF (Lebanese Front), formed by christian clans, the LNM (Lebanese National Movement), formed by the leftists and the PLO. Other participants in the war included Syria. (Kingston & Ochsenwald, paras.7-8)

The IDF forces launched the so-called "siege of Beirut " in 1982 in which Israel military forces invaded the capital city of Beirut, specifically the west sector of the city in which the IDF was able to remove the PLO forces from Lebanon as they fled and established new

headquarters in Tunisia. It was from 1982 to 1985 that the IDF committed violent acts against the Palestinian refugees as Christian militias allowed the IDF to present themselves in refugee camps where it is estimated that thousands of Palestinians lost their lives. It was by mid- 1985 that Israel forces were withdrawn from Lebanon. (Kingston & Ochsenwald ,paras.7-8).It was during this time that one of the soldiers that raided Beirut and that was part of the IDF during the Lebanon war was israeli filmmaker Ari Folman who, in order to share his experience as a member of the IDF and to deal with the trauma he suffered decided to direct and write an animated feature film titled *Waltz with Bashir* (2008).

6. Analysis of Waltz with Bashir (2008)

Waltz with Bashir is a 2008 animated film created by screenwriter, producer, music composer and filmmaker Ari Folman. Before becoming a world renowned filmmaker, Folman served in the IDF during the 1980's where he took part in the Lebanon war as he became a witness of the Sabra and Shatila Massacre. *Waltz with Bashir* (2008) follows the story of ex-soldier and filmmaker Ari Folman that, one day, meets with his friend Boas, who talks to Ari about a recurrent dream where 26 angry dogs chase him through the streets.

It is after this conversation that Ari finds out that, although he also was part of the IDF and he was present during Israel's invasion of Beirut, he is unable to recall any memories whatsoever as if his brain has deleted those memories in order to protect himself from trauma. It is later that night that Ari has a vision of his time during the war. After having this vision, the Israeli filmmaker recalls that this vision has a connection to the massacres of Sabra and Shatila but this does not mean anything as he cannot place this vision in time.

Troubled by this vision he visits an old friend who is a therapist and he encourages him to seek for the two men who accompanied him in that moment although he warns him that due to the nature of the human memory it can be a made up memory to maybe protect him from something or maybe mask something really important to him. Ari decides to follow his

friend's advice and travels to the Netherlands to visit Carmi Can'an, an old friend of Ari who served in the war with him. After interviewing him, Ari goes on to interview multiple war veterans who shared the battlefield with him in order to understand what truly happened. In time, Ari starts to regain his memories and recalls being in the third or second ring of Israel soldiers that were involved in the massacre as Israel supporting Lebanese Christian Phalange militia penetrated the massacre in retaliation for the killing of Bachir. Ari learns that the mechanisms in his head had erased all these memories in order to protect him as he was one of the many IDF soldiers that took part in the massacre and he himself blocked those memories because he felt responsible for all the horror they had caused in Lebanon. (Waltz with Bashr, 2008)

But what relation might this movie have with Benedict Anderson's work? as Benedict Anderson said in his research, he believed that nationalisms were "imagined communities", if we recall the previous research we conducted based on Sanjaume i Calvet's (2016) research on Anderson and imagined communities we can say that nationalisms, as religion or kinships does to, are set to divide people in different communities with different religions and traditions as we can see, Israelites are different from Lebanese, Palestinians or Syrians as they both share different ethnicity, religion and traditions.

These differences provoke a collision that ultimately starts leading to war and conflicts. The problem with the conflicts and war that they generate is that this imaginary concepts of religion and nationalism that we have created come to create real life outcomes like wars, hunger or death as, people like Ari, who belonged to a jewish and israeli community where forced to enlist in the IDF and were told that they need to fight other human beings that believe that they should no exist and therefore they go to war to kill each other.

What nationalism, pride and religion cause is that many people like Ari Folman or his fellow war veterans will be left with unbearable traumas that they will not heal and probably will see

their last days still being haunted by those demons they had to face years ago. What Folman does with this film is project his own trauma by showing all the horrible things he had to experience because of national pride and Israel's hunger to destroy Palestinians.

Cinema serves as a crucial tool for Ari to explain his own trauma as, it is through the big screen that, with the cinematic identifications and the kuleshov effect that, we are able to get a better understanding of what is happening inside his head and how it might feel to be on his own shoes. Through the Kuleshov effect (Hensley and Prince, 1992) we can experience that the contrast of images creates our own reality and therefore we have seen that the contrast of images can generate a feeling of belief in what we are seeing as we can feel the emotions in the picture because of the contrast of images.

Now it is through the cinematic identifications that I have seen that Folman uses animation as a way to express himself better as it is a technique that can be used to portray dreams and subconsciousness in a better way. It is through primary identifications that we are able to engage as the spectator and the beholders as our third person view of the movie makes us feel as if we are an invisible entity that is being shown everything by Folman, who is the one that tells the story (Reich & Richmond, 2015). It is with the cinematic secondary identifications that create the sentimental part of the movie as, the movie can create different emotions of empathy towards the IDF soldiers as they were the ones that had to go through the horrors as we can see that the film shows only the side of Israel and few images and characters are shown from the Lebanese and Palestinian perspectives (Reich & Richmond, 2015). It is through my research on cinematic identifications that I have learned that cinema is a tool that can be used to show and promote different emotions and political values as we can represent it from the perspective we want. As Harris (2015) argued:

“(...)simplistically divided the Arab population into two archetypes: the sympathetic Bedouin, whom the Zionists might civilize while he in turn would teach the young

pioneers secrets of the land, and the danger-ous and ignominious Arab, who could not be trusted.” (pg.222)

Finally, in my research we have seen that the Israeli film industry has always used cinema as a political and national tool to portray different values as we saw in films like “*Hill 24 doesn't answer*”(1955) where israel cinema has tend to promote and portray values of racial superiority, pureness and national pride against the muslims.

7.Conclusions

It is in conclusion to my research that I have found that cinema can be a great tool to understand how concepts like nationalism, identity or trauma work and also how it can be used as a tool that can help to express these concepts.

Through these processes of cinematic identifications we can make our own interpretation of reality then we can express emotional or political values through them as in different ways audiences might engage more with it or not.

The Israel film industry has used cinema as a tool to project different values related to national identity, zionism or other different representations of racial groups like arabs. By conducting my research I decided to look at the work of Ari Folman as his film *Waltz with Bashr* (2008), film that deals with war trauma, that it is concepts like nationalism o religion, concepts described by Benedict Anderson as “imagined communities”, that create imaginary ideas in people’s minds and, it is this own ideas the ones that generate real concepts or events like war or death which people like Ari experienced during his IDF serving period.

Finally, it is the emotional and political aspect of cinema that, through techniques of identification, is able to make imaginary concepts believable, making us feel attached and identified with them therefore believing a different reality and, film industries like Israel or even Hollywood, use this techniques to implement imaginary values that will create destructive real events.

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